

Damage Analysis of Fibrous Composites

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper the mechanisms behind the cut-off of the stress peak at notches in fibrous composites are investigated using the fictitious crack model (FCM). In the intense energy region close to the notch, a fictitious crack is assumed to form when the uniaxial tensile strength is exceeded. On the surfaces of this fictitious crack, cohesive forces act. These forces reduce with increased width of the fictitious crack and vanish at a certain crack width. Hereafter the crack is considered as a real crack. The reduction of the cohesive forces can be assumed to follow various curves. A common feature for all curves is, however, that the area under the curve is equal to the fracture energy G_C . It should also be emphasized that the fictitious crack merely represents a damage zone in the composite rather than a sharp crack.

Results, both experimental and based on the FCM-model, are presented for the tensile fracture strength of several graphite/epoxy [0/90/±45] laminates containing different types of notches. Experimental data from the tension tests correlate reasonably well with those obtained from FCM analyses. Results for laminates containing circular holes are compared with the theories of Whitney et al.

INTRODUCTION

In the study of the tensile fracture of continuous fibre-reinforced composites, attention has been directed to a phenomena that has become known as the "hole size effect". In other words, in tension specimens that contain various sizes of circular holes, larger holes cause greater strength reduction than smaller holes. This effect cannot be explained by a classical stress concentration factor. Therefore, attempts have been made to explain the phenomena by using linear fracture mechanics (LEFM). Waddoups et al [1] were among the first to apply LEFM to notched composites. For laminates containing circular holes they argued that the material contained a damage area adjacent to the hole which was analogous to a crack. On the basis of experimental results, they used the Bowie solution [2] for the stress intensity factor for cracks emanating from a circular hole in an isotropic plate to explain the hole size effect. The usual one-parameter LEFM model, using only fracture toughness, K_{IC} , was replaced by a two-parameter LEFM model in which the length of the damage zone a was the second parameter.

In a number of papers, Nuismer and Whitney [3,4] have presented a theoretical basis, experimental verification and practical application of stress criteria which are similar to the inherent flaw criterion. However, LEFM is not applied, but the stress distribution ahead of the notch is obtained using linear elasticity. They introduced two fracture models called the point and average stress criteria. The point stress criterion assumes that failure occurs when the stress over some distance, d_0 , away from the discontinuity is equal to the strength of the unnotched material, whereas the average stress criterion assumes that failure occurs when the average stress over some distance, a_0 , ahead of the discontinuity equals the unnotched laminate strength. In each case a characteristic size was employed that might be considered to be related to a damage zone immediately ahead of the notch. Thus, the parameters in the point and average stress criteria are the unnotched tensile strength and the length of the damage zone.

Pipes et al [5] presented a three-parameter relationship for the strength of notched composites which was based on the works by Waddoups et al [1] and Nuismer and Whitney [3,4]. Beside the unnotched tensile strength, a notch sensitivity factor m and an experimental parameter C was introduced.

The criteria mentioned above are all of empirical type, i.e. they all rely upon some parameter, e.g. a , d_0 , a_0 , C , m etc, which has to be chosen in such a way that the experimental results are approximated by the theory. These parameters can not be calculated or postulated on the basis of fundamental data of the laminate, but they are selected on a best-fit basis. A theory by which the notched fracture strength could be computed from known fundamental material data would be much more appealing. In this paper calculations of fracture strength for notched $[0,90, \pm 45]_{2S}$ graphite/epoxy composites based on the fictitious crack model (FCM) is presented. This model was originally used by Hillerborg et al [6] and Moder [7] for fracture analysis of concrete and cement. The FCM-model fulfills the requirements discussed above, i.e. only basic material parameters such as stiffnesses, unnotched fracture stress σ_0 and fracture energy G_c are required as input parameters. The entire process of crack formation and crack growth, both stable and unstable, can be modelled. The fracture load can be calculated for various shapes of notches and not only circular holes.

THE FICTITIOUS CRACK MODEL [8]

The basic principle of FCM is to gather all microcracks and other local fractures, such as fibre fracture, fibre pull-out, post-debond friction, matrix micro-cracking etc. [9-11], to a fictitious crack, see Fig 1. From a computational point of view, the fictitious crack is identical to a real crack with uniting stresses acting on the crack surfaces. The fictitious crack is formed when the unnotched tensile strength σ_0 of the material is exceeded, Fig 2.

Fig 1 Modelling of damage zone as a fictitious crack: (a) Damage zone (b) Fictitious crack.

Fig 2 Stress vs strain and crack opening: (a) stress-strain curve of unnotched composite, (b) reduction of the stress acting on the crack surfaces with crack opening $2w$. The area under the curve is equal to the fracture energy G_c .

When the crack opening $2w$ increases, due to an increase of the external load, the uniting stresses are reduced, Fig 2b. This reduction can be expressed with a general function $f(w)$, eqn (1)

$$\sigma = f(w) \quad (1)$$

The area under the $\sigma - w$ curve corresponds to the fracture energy G_c , Fig 2b. The fracture energy G_c represents the sum of all energies dissipated in the above mentioned various fracture mechanisms.

Fig 3 Crack growth according to the FCM (a) real and fictitious cracks (b) computational fracture load.

At a limiting value of w , which is denoted w_c , the stress is reduced to zero and a real crack is formed, Fig 3a. Upon a further increase of the external load the real crack grows. The growth is generally stable in a first phase and then it changes to be unstable. The load at which the crack growth changes from stable to unstable is in the following taken as the fracture load according to the computations, Fig 3b.

A very nice property of the FCM-model is that both information, stable growth and unstable growth of cracks can be followed for quasi-static loadings. The later is true if the analysis is displacement controlled. This general property of modelling the behaviour of an unloaded and undamaged structure up to fracture is unique for FCM and has no counterpart in either conventional fracture mechanics or the criteria developed for composites such as the inherent flaw, point or average stress criteria.

Various approximations can be used both for the stress-strain curve and for the stress-crack opening curve. In this work a linear stress-strain curve is assumed, i.e. the material is assumed to be linearly elastic. For the stress-crack opening curve two different approximations are used, Fig 4. In the first one, a constant stress σ_0 is assumed to act on the surfaces of the crack as long as the crack opening is less than $2w_{c1}$, eqn (2)

$$w_{c1} = \frac{G_c}{2\sigma_0} \quad (2)$$

Fig 4 Constant and linearly decreasing stress-crack opening curve.

In the second case a linearly decreasing stress-crack opening curve is employed with the limiting value $2w_{c2}$ of the crack opening, eqn (3)

$$w_{c2} = \frac{G_c}{\sigma_0} \quad (3)$$

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The material used in the experimental program consisted of Thornel 300 graphite fibers in Hy-E-1034 epoxy resin. The prepreg materials were hand laid-up for the desired angles and cured according to manufacturers recommended cure procedure. The final product was obtained as sheets with a matrix content of approximately 35%. A total of 24 rectangular specimens with different notches were tested, but all specimens have the same width $w = 140$ mm and length $L = 236$ mm, see Fig 5. All notches were produced with tools covered with diamond, in order to get

smooth surfaces and sharp edges. The laminates tested were of quasi-isotropic type containing 16 plies oriented as $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2S}$.

All specimens were tested in an Amsler machine at a constant cross-head rate of 1 mm/min and the grips were fixed in such a way that neither bending nor torsion influenced the specimens. Strains were recorded at several places on the specimens for those containing small notches. During each test, the applied load were monitored and recorded continuously.

Fig 5 Geometry of tested specimens containing different notches. Positions of strain gauges A and B.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The specimens tested are listed in Table 1 and their dimensions L , W , R , and b are shown in Fig 5. From Table 1 it is shown that the thickness t differ somewhat for large and small notches, and this is due to the fact that the specimens were produced from two different sheets.

Specimen No.	t (mm)	b (mm)	h (mm)	σ_N (MPa)	σ_N/σ_0 (-)	Max. strain (ϵ_A)(%)	Var. (%)	Max. strain (ϵ_B)(%)	Var. (%)
Large circular hole diameter ϕ 40-1,2,3	2.15	40	40	205.8	0.355	+0.6 -1.3			
Large rectangular hole radius $R=20$ -1,2,3	2.23	40	80	234.5	0.404	+1.1 -1.2			
Large rectangular hole radius $R=10$ -1,2,3	2.20	40	80	226.2	0.390	+4.0 -4.7			
Large rectangular hole radius $R=0$ -1,2,3	2.20	40	80	215.6	0.372	+2.7 -4.0			
Small circular hole diameter ϕ 20-1,2,3	2.06	20	20	240.2	0.414	+2.2 -3.5	0.43	+2.3 -4.3	0.97 0.
Small rectangular hole radius $R=10$ -1,2,3	2.05	20	40	289.2	0.499	+1.2 -1.2	0.48	+1.0 -1.0	0.90 +2.2 -1.1
Small rectangular hole radius $R=5$ -1,2,3	2.07	20	40	272.1	0.469	+2.7 -2.0	0.44	+2.3 -2.5	0.83 +6.0 -3.6
Small rectangular hole radius $R=0$ -1,2,3	2.05	20	40	272.0	0.469	+2.0 -2.6	0.46	+2.2 -4.3	0.76 +5.3 -3.9

Table 1 Experimental data obtained from notched specimens and average specimen dimensions.

Three specimens were tested at each notch-size and their average value of the notched strength are presented in Table 1. Note that, the discrepancy for the notched strengths are less than 5%. A comparison between the notched strengths for large notches, shows that specimens containing rectangular notches with radius $R = 20$ mm are capable to bear the highest load, while the specimens containing circular notches bear the smallest. But most remarkable is that specimens containing rectangular holes with radius $R = 0$ mm are capable to bear higher load than those containing circular notches, particularly when the value of b is the

same. This tendency is the same for the specimens containing small notches. The ratios of the experimental determined notched and unnotched tensile strengths, shown in Table 4, shall be compared with those obtained from the numerical calculations, which are presented in sec. 5. Fig 6 shows all the specimens containing small notches after complete fracture. Obviously the fracture zones were initiated at places where the stress concentration factor (SCF) was largest.

Fig 6 Failed $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2S}$ notched specimens.

For all specimens containing the small notch, load versus strains were monitored and recorded continuously. Fig 5 shows the positions in which the strain gauges were applied.

Straingauge A is placed in such a way that strain-states from the notch and the tabs do not influence the measurements. At least two strain gauges, B, were placed beside the notch in order to get the behavior of load-strain curves at the expected fracture zones. Fracture zones were assumed to be developed at places where the stress concentration factor (SCF) was largest. The values of SCF were obtained from finite element calculations. The maximum values of the strain at A and B given in Table 1 are the average value for the three specimens used for each type of notch. Note that, since $[0,90,\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminates were tested, the strains were always measured in the fiberdirection. The high values of strains obtained from gauges B indicates that the areas are intense energy regions.

The unnotched tensile strength for the $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate was obtained from experimental data. The quotient between the fracture load and the cross-section area for each of the three specimens tested yields an average value of the unnotched tensile strength σ_0 according to Table 2, which also shows their dimensions, where l denotes the length between the tabs, d their width and t the thickness.

Results obtained from load-strain measurements performed on the specimens, make it possible to determine Young's modulus for the material based on experimental data. The average value of Young's modulus based on experimental data, E^* , and that calculated from laminate theory, E , are present in Table 2 and the difference between these values are less than 2%. It must be pointed out that the load-strain curves always showed a linear behavior, and since $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminates were tested, the strains used in calculation of E^* were measured in the fiber-direction.

Specimen	l (mm)	d (mm)	t (mm)	σ_0 (MPa)	Var.(%)	E^* (MPa)	Var.(%)	E (MPa)
Unnotched specimens - 1,2,3	100.0	22.20	2.05	580.7	-2.4	55534	-0.5	54510

Table 2 Experimental data obtained from unnotched specimens and average specimen dimension.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

General remarks

In the present applications of the FCM-model, all the eight different configurations of the tested laminates were studied. The geometries of the analysed laminates are shown in Fig 5 and the stiffness properties of the laminas used are given in Table 3.

Stiffness property	Value	Units
Young's modulus in the fiber direction, E_{11}	143.0	GPa
Young's modulus in the transverse direction, E_{22}	11.0	GPa
Shear modulus G_{12}	4.0	GPa
Major Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	0.35	-

Table 3 Stiffness properties of graphite/epoxy lamina

Schematic finite element meshes for the laminate containing the large circular hole used at the computations are shown in Fig 7. Three different sizes of the elements layout along the x-axis were modeled in order to get a check of the discretization errors in the analysis. For all the notched laminates the damage or the fictitious crack was assumed to be developed in a mode-I sense and at a place where the stress concentration factor is largest. In all computations the general purpose finite element code GENFEM-3 developed by Glemberg et al [12-14] was used. This computer program make it possible to generate a condensed stiffness matrix, used in the computations, also in such a case where the extension of the fictitious crack does not lie on a line of symmetry. For example, Fig 8 shows such a case and the finite element breakdown for the laminate containing the large rectangular notch. Four-node quadrilateral finite elements of a superparametric type with straight or curved sides are used in this study.

Fig 7 Finite element breakdown for the laminate containing large circular hole.

Fig 8 Finite element breakdown for the laminate containing large rectangular notch.

Calculation of the fracture energy, G_{IC}

Kim [15] generated crack-growth-resistance curves (K_R -curves) for both bend and tension tests, where graphite/epoxy T300/5208 composite laminates, $[0/±45/90]_S$, were investigated. Critical values of the stress-intensity factor under mode-I condition, K_{IC} were obtained in this investigation. For 32-ply bend specimens a K_{IC} -value of 39 MPa/m was reported and for those containing 64 plies, 36.2 MPa/m. A similar investigation for determining the fracture toughness of the T300/1034 material used here will be presented in a future report. Looking to these results, ignoring the thickness effect and the difference in laminate orientation, an average value of the fracture toughness value obtained by Kim will be used in order

to calculate a value of the fracture energy, G_{IC} .

Thus, for a homogeneous quasi-isotropic linear elastic material, the fracture energy can be determined for the case of a crack lying along a plane of symmetry and under mode-I and plane stress conditions [16] according to:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{K_{IC}^2}{E^*} \quad (4)$$

where G_{IC} = Fracture energy under mode-I condition
 K_{IC} = Fracture toughness under mode-I condition
 E^* = Young's modulus for the laminate experimental determined.

Using the average value of the fracture toughness value obtained by Kim and the average value of E^* (55534 MPa) experimental determined, eqn (4) gives G_{IC} = 25.5 kJ/m². This value of the fracture energy gives a comprehension of the magnitude of values expected from our tests, and will be used in calculations of notched strengths for the notched laminates reported here.

Large and small notches

For all eight laminates studied here each notched strength was predicted using the FCM technique and the computations were performed on a small computer. In all computations the unnotched tensile strength $\sigma_0 = 580.7$ MPa and the fracture energy $G_C = 25.5$ kJ/m² were used as input-data, besides the uncondensed stiffness matrix corresponding to each notched laminate. In each computation the linearly decreasing stress-crack opening curve (see Fig 4) was employed with the limiting value $2w_{C2}$ of the crack opening according to eqn (3). The solution procedure used in the computations is described in detail in ref [17] and only its main features will be given here. Therefore, consider Fig 9 showing the external stress σ versus the total crack length (a+c) for the laminate containing the large circular hole, where the solid and dashed curves represent results using element lengths of 2.5 mm (coarse mesh) and 1.25 mm (fine mesh), respectively, along the fictitious crack, see also Fig 7.

Fig 9 External stress σ vs total crack length a+c for laminate containing circular notch with $\phi 40$ mm. $G_C = 20$ kJ/m².

A fictitious crack will be initiated when the nodal load corresponding to node 1 (drawing at the bottom of Fig 9) exceeds the half nodal tensile strength which equals the unnotched strength σ_0 multiplied by the half element length b and the laminate thickness h. At the same time the displacement w_1 , corresponding to node 1, is hold equal to zero. These two conditions must be valid simultaneously and constitute the fracture criterion. The external stress σ is then computed (point A in Fig 9). In the next step a fictitious crack has been developed (which equals the element length 2.5 mm) and the nodal load corresponding to node 2 has reached the tensile strength equals to $2\sigma_0bh$. The nodal load corresponding to node 1 is reduced according to the linearly decreasing σ -w curve. At the same time the displacement w_1 is checked with respect to the limiting value w_{C2} . In this case the crack growth is still stable and w_1 less than w_{C2} , therefore the fictitious

crack allows to grow further. The procedure is repeated until the crack growth becomes unstable which happens after that the external stress σ has reached its maximum value (point B in Fig 9). The external stress value at which the crack growth changes from stable to unstable is in the following taken as the fracture stress. It should be added that there is no discrepancy between the maximal external stress value using the coarse or the fine mesh. In the following computations the coarse mesh along the fictitious crack was used.

In Figs 10 thru 13 graphical comparison of the experimentally obtained notched strengths with the predicted is shown, where notched to unnotched strength, σ_N/σ_0 , is plotted versus the fracture energy, G_c . In all figures the solid dots represent the average experimental value, the vertical line through the dots represent the data spread and the solid and dashed curves represent the predicted values for small and large notched laminates, respectively. The predicted notched strengths for $G_c = 25.5 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, which are represented by circles, give higher values compared to the experimental average values, except in the case for the laminate containing the larger circular notch. For all notched laminates the discrepancy is less than 8%. On the other hand the value used for the fracture energy is uncertain and a definite conclusion about the results can not be done until a more reliable value has been investigated. However, it appears that a value of about 20 kJ/m^2 should give an excellent agreement between the predicted and the experimental notched strengths. Furthermore, the experimental average values plotted in Figs 10 thru 13 indicates that the fracture energy not seems to be affected by neither the shape nor the size of the notch for all notched laminates except those containing the large circular notch.

Fig 10 Comparison of predicted and experimental notched strengths for laminates containing circular notches.

Fig 12 Comparison of predicted and experimental notched strengths for laminates containing rectangular notches with radius $r = 10 \text{ mm}$ and $R = 5 \text{ mm}$.

Fig 11 Comparison of predicted and experimental notched strengths for laminates containing rectangular notches with radius $R = 20 \text{ mm}$ and $R = 10 \text{ mm}$.

Fig 13 Comparison of predicted and experimental notched strengths for laminates containing rectangular notches.

Comparison with theories of Whitney et al for circular notches

For laminates containing circular notches (with notch sizes of $\varnothing 40$ mm and $\varnothing 20$ mm) it is possible to compare notched strengths obtained from FCM-computations with those predicted from the point- and the average stress criterion developed by Whitney et al [3,4]. The input data used in the FCM-computations are those presented in the section before. The predicted notched strengths calculated from the point- and the average stress criteria were obtained using the unnotched tensile strength $\sigma_0 = 580.7$ MPa and the characteristic distances, reported in ref [4], $d_0 = 1.02$ mm and $a_0 = 3.8$ mm respectively. In the performed calculations consideration have been taken to the isotropic finite width correction factor given in ref [4].

Graphical comparison of the experimentally obtained notched strengths with the predicted values are shown in Fig 14, where σ_N/σ_0 is plotted versus notch size. The solid dots represent the average experimental value, the vertical line through the dots represents the data spread and the solid and dashed curves represent the predicted values using the average and point stress failure criterion, respectively. Predicted notched strengths from the FCM-computations are marked with crosses for two different values of the fracture energy. From fig 4 it is shown that predicted notched strengths obtained from FCM-computations agree quite good with those experimental determined and differ less than 6% for the two values of the fracture energy, while those predicted from the average stress criterion are somewhat higher.

Fig 14 Comparison of predicted and experimental notched strengths for laminates containing circular notch.

DISCUSSION

Prediction of notched strengths for $[0/90/_{\pm 45}]_{2S}$ graphite/epoxy laminates containing various types of notches has been performed using the FCM technique. In the FCM-model only fundamental material data such as stiffness, unnotched fracture stress σ_0 and fracture energy G_C are required as input parameters. Comparison between the experimental and predicted notched strength for all the laminates studied show good agreement and the discrepancy is less than 8%. While the value of the fracture energy is somewhat uncertain a definite conclusion about the results can not be done. However, it is interesting to note that a fracture value of about 20 kJ/m² should give an excellent agreement between predicted and experimental notched strengths for all laminates (see Fig 10-13). For the laminates containing circular notches it is shown that predicted notched strengths obtained from FCM-computations (with $G_C = 25.5$ or 20. kJ/m²) agree quite good with those experimental determined, while those predicted from the average stress criterion are somewhat higher.

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